

MEDICAL SCIENCES

АНТИМИКРОБНОЕ ДЕЙСТВИЕ ЭКСТРАКТОВ И ЭФИРНЫХ МАСЕЛ РАСТЕНИЙ СЕМЕЙСТВА LAMIACEAE; МЯТЫ, БАЗИЛИКА, ЧАБРЕЦА, РОЗМАРИНА И ШАЛФЕЯ ПРОТИВ АНТИБИОТИКОРЕЗИСТЕНТНЫХ ГРАМ-ОТРИЦАТЕЛЬНЫХ БАКТЕРИЙ, ВЫЗЫВАЮЩИХ ИНФЕКЦИИ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПОМОЩЬЮ

Гулиева А.Р.

Магистрант, Кафедра Микробиологии и Иммунологии

Самедзаде Р.Э.

*Кандидат наук по микробиологии Лаборатории “Inci”,
Центральное отделение, Отдел Микробиологии*

Байрамлы Р.Б.

*Доцент, Кафедра Медицинской Микробиологии И Иммунологии
Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет, Баку, Азербайджан*

ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTS OF EXTRACTS AND ESSENTIAL OILS OBTAINED FROM LAMIACEAE FAMILY PLANTS; MINT, BASIL, THYME, ROSEMARY, AND SAGE AGAINST ANTIBIOTIC-RESISTANT GRAM-NEGATIVE BACTERIA CAUSING HEALTHCARE-ASSOCIATED INFECTIONS

Guliyeva A.

Master's student, Department of Microbiology and Immunology

Samedzade R.

PhD in Microbiology, Inci Laboratories, Central Branch, Department of Microbiology

Bayramli R.

*Associate Professor, Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Аннотация

Антибиотикорезистентность бактерий, вызывающих инфекции, связанные с оказанием медицинской помощи, получила широкое распространение и превратилась в одну из серьёзнейших проблем здравоохранения современности. Наряду с постепенной утратой эффективности антибиотиков и синтетических препаратов возрастает интерес к растительным средствам. Растения семейства *Lamiaceae* широко применяются в народной медицине. Установлено, что экстракты и эфирные масла этих растений обладают выраженной антибактериальной активностью.

Abstract

Antibiotic resistance of bacteria causing healthcare-associated infections has become widespread and represents one of the major public health problems in modern times. Alongside the gradual loss of effectiveness of antibiotics and synthetic drugs, there is a growing interest in plant-based preparations. Plants belonging to the *Lamiaceae* family have been widely used in traditional medicine. Extracts and essential oils derived from these plants have been shown to possess strong antibacterial activity.

Ключевые слова: Инфекции, связанные с оказанием медицинской помощи, грамотрицательные бактерии, антибиотикорезистентность, семейство Яснотковые *Lamiaceae*, антимикробное действие.

Keywords: Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), Gram-negative bacteria, Antibiotic resistance, *Lamiaceae* family, Antimicrobial activity.

Nosocomial infections are considered as a global public health problem, causing high rates of morbidity and mortality among hospitalized patients each year. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), nosocomial infections—also referred to as healthcare-associated infections (HAIs)—are defined as infections that occur 48–72 hours after hospital admission or discharge. Infections with longer incubation periods, particularly those caused by hepatitis viruses (HBV, HCV), the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), and tuberculosis, may develop within hospital settings and persist for weeks or even years. According to WHO data, HAIs are responsible for approximately 40,000 deaths annually. The incidence of HAIs reaches up to

25% in developing countries and 5–15% in developed ones. The risk of HAIs is higher in neonates, the elderly, patients with chronic diseases, those receiving immunosuppressive therapy, and individuals whose immunity is weakened as a result of medical or surgical interventions [1].

Among the main causative agents of healthcare-associated infections, Gram-negative bacteria currently represent a particular concern. The situation is further complicated by the increasing resistance of these microorganisms to antimicrobial drugs. Several factors contribute to this decline in antibiotic effectiveness, including the reduction in discovery and development of new antibiotics, difficulties in screening novel

chemical compounds, high production costs, long development times, and the complex design and implementation of clinical trials [2].

Species of *Acinetobacter baumannii* were identified between 1986 and 2003 as major etiological agents of pneumonia in intensive care units (ICUs) across the United States. Resistance to carbapenems (such as imipenem and meropenem) among these bacteria has created significant therapeutic challenges. Recent studies revealed that 26.4% of 679 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 36.8% of 427 *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains associated with ventilator-associated pneumonia were resistant to carbapenems [2].

One of the most serious problems encountered in nosocomial infections is the dissemination of carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* species. The carbapenemase synthesized by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* leads to reduced susceptibility to all cephalosporins (including cefepime), monobactams (such as aztreonam), and carbapenems. Carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* have been detected in hospitals across at least 20 U.S.A states and several other regions of the world, including South America, Israel, China, and Europe. These β -lactamases are typically encoded by mobile genetic elements such as plasmids and transposons, facilitating rapid dissemination of resistance among Gram-negative bacteria. In addition, extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) (*bla*_CTX-M-15 gene) and plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance genes (*qnrA* and *qnrB*) are among the most widely distributed resistance determinants worldwide [3].

Historical evidence indicates that since ancient times, humans have utilized plants both as a food source and for medicinal purposes. From the earliest stages of civilization to the present day, plants have been widely used as sources of medicine and raw materials obtained through various extraction methods. Throughout history, numerous diseases such as jaundice and diabetes mellitus have been treated using plant-based remedies.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately half of the world's population primarily relies on plant-derived preparations for healthcare and disease management. Furthermore, about 25% of prescription drugs in developed countries are derived from plants, including well-known examples such as quinine, aspirin, and reserpine [4]. It is estimated that at least 25% of the active ingredients in newly developed chemotherapeutic drugs are of plant origin. In addition, many modern synthetic drugs have active compounds structurally similar to natural molecules found in medicinal plants.

The demand for plants used in the pharmaceutical industry continues to increase in both developed and developing countries. This trend is largely due to the relatively lower cost of herbal drugs compared to synthetic chemicals, their minimal side effects and toxicity, and their natural origin [5].

In recent years, the growing number of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms has made the treatment of infections increasingly difficult. Therefore, the use of medicinal plants as an alternative or complementary option to conventional antibiotics has gained great

interest, and plants are now widely studied for this purpose [6].

The family *Lamiaceae* is one of the most diverse and widely distributed plant families from an ethnomedicinal perspective, with its therapeutic importance primarily associated with its high content of essential oils. These oils play a crucial role in pesticide production, pharmaceuticals, perfumery, and the cosmetic industries. According to WHO estimates, 70–80% of the world's population uses medicinal and aromatic plants for therapeutic purposes [7].

In Azerbaijan, the *Lamiaceae* family is among the largest groups of angiosperms [flowering plants]. Recent botanical studies have shown that the family is represented in the country by 37 genera and 241 taxa (including species and subspecies). Among them, 204 are species and 37 are subspecies, with 19 taxa being endemic to Azerbaijan. The highest diversity of *Lamiaceae* species is found particularly in the mountainous regions of Nakhchivan and the Quba section of the Greater Caucasus [8].

Aromatic plants belonging to the *Lamiaceae* family have a wide range of traditional, pharmaceutical, and food industry applications. These plants are known for their properties such as stimulating blood circulation and digestion, enhancing the central nervous system, and possessing expectorant, spasmolytic, antiseptic, diuretic, carminative, and tonic characteristics. [9].

Commonly used members of this family such as rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*), thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), mint (*Mentha piperita*), and sage (*Salvia officinalis*) are traditionally employed in the treatment of gastritis, dermatitis, bronchitis, and inflammatory conditions. Among these, rosemary and sage are particularly notable for their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, which have been extensively studied and applied in both traditional and modern medicine [10].

The genus *Thymus*, belonging to the *Lamiaceae* family, is notable for its numerous species. To date, approximately 928 species of *Thymus* have been identified across Europe, North Africa, Asia, South America, and Australia. Among them, *Thymus serpyllum* and *Thymus vulgaris* are particularly notable due to their chemical composition and therapeutic potential [11]. The rich phytochemical profile of thyme, which includes flavonoids, phenolic compounds, aromatic derivatives, saponins, tannins, iridoids, and quinones, underlies its extensive use in medicine [12].

Originating from the Mediterranean region, thyme has been used since ancient times in both culinary and medicinal applications. The essential oil of *Thymus vulgaris* contains more than 60 different compounds, most of which exhibit strong antiseptic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties. One of its principal constituents, thymol (10–64%), is responsible for many of its pharmacological effects. Research on thymol-based pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic products has demonstrated its therapeutic potential in respiratory, nervous, and cardiovascular disorders. In addition, thymol possesses antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antispasmodic effects and may demonstrate growth-promoting and immunomodulatory effects [13].

The genus *Mentha* includes plants whose essential oils are rich in menthol-type terpenes. The highest essential oil yield is found in the leaves, which contributes to their significant economic value in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Although the genus comprises only about 25 species worldwide, the range of biological activities displayed by *Mentha* species is remarkable, including antihypertensive, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiallergic, biopesticidal, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral properties. These pharmacological effects are attributed mainly to compounds such as menthol, menthone, 1,8-cineole, carvone, limonene, β -caryophyllene, and pulegone [14].

Essential oils obtained from mint are among the most commonly used in the pharmaceutical and food industries, particularly in cough syrups, chewing gums, confectionery, and beverages. The leaves and essential oil of *Mentha piperita* exhibit gastrostimulant and therapeutic effects and have been reported to possess antibacterial, antiviral, antiparasitic, and antifungal activities [15].

Ocimum basilicum, is a highly valued aromatic and medicinal plant. The essential oils extracted from basil are widely used in the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries. The genus comprises around 160 species, and its essential oils are rich in terpenoids and phenylpropanoids, including methyl cinnamate, linalool, thymol, camphor, citral, eugenol, and geraniol [16]. Basil leaves and essential oils are traditionally used for the treatment of headache, common cold, diarrhea, and renal insufficiency, and their active components are known to stimulate the digestive system and relieve pain and fatigue [17].

Salvia officinalis, is a perennial shrub encompassing approximately 900 species distributed worldwide and widely cultivated in Europe and North America. *S. officinalis* has long been used in culinary and traditional medicine. In Asian and Latin American folk medicine, it is employed in the treatment of ulcers, gout, rheumatism, inflammation, dizziness, tremors, paralysis, diarrhea, and hyperglycemia. Phytochemical studies of its flowers, leaves, and stems have revealed the presence of diverse bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, carbohydrates, fatty acids, glycosides, phenolic compounds, polyacetylenes, steroids, terpenes, monoterpenoids, triterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and waxes [18].

Rosmarinus officinalis is a medicinal plant of Mediterranean origin that is now cultivated worldwide. In addition to its therapeutic applications, it is commonly used as a spice and food preservative. The pharmacological properties of *R. officinalis* are attributed to its bioactive molecules and phytochemical compounds, which exhibit anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiproliferative, antitumor, protective, and inhibitory effects. In traditional medicine, rosemary has been used in the treatment of asthma, atherosclerosis, cataracts, renal colic, hepatotoxicity, gastric ulcers, and inflammatory diseases [19].

A study investigating the essential oil of thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*) revealed strong inhibitory effects against several oral pathogens, including *Streptococcus pyogenes* (*S. pyogenes*), *Streptococcus mutans* (*S. Mutans*), *Candida albicans* (*C. Albicans*), *Aggregatibacter*

actinomycetemcomitans (*A. Actinomycetemcomitans*), and *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (*P. gingivalis*). Among the tested strains, *S. pyogenes* isolated from patients with pharyngitis showed the highest sensitivity to thyme essential oil. Furthermore, the essential oil of *T. serpyllum* exhibited greater antimicrobial activity against clinical *S. pyogenes* strains than streptomycin and ampicillin, with a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 2.5 ± 0.23 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [20].

Another study evaluated the antimicrobial effects of extracts from 46 medicinal and spice plants against *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L. monocytogenes*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. Aureus*), *Bacillus cereus* (*B. cereus*), *Salmonella anatum* (*S. anatum*) v α *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). Results demonstrated that essential oils from species belonging to the genera *Origanum* and *Thymus* exhibited potent antifungal and antibacterial activity. Gram-positive bacteria were found to be more sensitive to these extracts than Gram-negative ones, with *S. aureus* being the most susceptible strain. Moreover, it was observed that the essential oils of *Origanum* and *Thymus* species showed no mutagenic effects on *Salmonella typhimurium*, indicating their safety for use as natural food preservatives [21].

In a study conducted in Pakistan, the antimicrobial activity of *T. vulgaris* essential oil was assessed using the disk diffusion method. Test microorganisms included clinical isolates of *Salmonella spp.*, *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, and *E. coli* obtained from Bolan Medical Complex Hospital. The highest antimicrobial activity was recorded against *E. coli* (22 mm inhibition zone), while *Streptococcus spp.* exhibited the lowest sensitivity (8 mm inhibition zone) [22].

Research on four thyme species: *T. vulgaris*, *T. zygis*, *T. serpyllum*, and *T. pulegioides*—showed that the essential oils from all four inhibited the growth of *Streptococcus mutans* significantly. The lowest colony-forming unit (CFU) values were recorded for *T. serpyllum* (1,750 CFU/mL), followed by *T. vulgaris* (3,500 CFU/mL), *T. zygis* (4,500 CFU/mL), and *T. pulegioides* (27,500 CFU/mL). The study concluded that *T. vulgaris* essential oil exhibited the strongest antimicrobial activity, while *T. zygis* showed the weakest effect [23].

A study by Sienkiewicz et al. examined the antibacterial activity of basil (*O. Basilicum*) and rosemary (*R. Officinalis*) essential oils against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and 60 clinical *E. coli* strains isolated from patients with respiratory, abdominal, urinary, and skin infections. The ESBL-positive *E. coli* strains tested were resistant to β -lactams, aminoglycosides, quinolones, cephalosporins, and β -lactam inhibitors such as sulbactam and tazobactam. However, all strains were sensitive to basil and rosemary essential oils, with basil oil demonstrating the highest activity against ESBL-positive *E. coli* strains. These findings emphasize the potential of essential oils in the treatment and prevention of nosocomial infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria [24].

In India, the antimicrobial effects of 21 essential oils were tested against four Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, *P. Vulgaris*) and two Gram-positive bacteria (*B. subtilis*, *S. Aureus*) at

four different concentrations. Among all samples, rosemary essential oil exhibited the strongest inhibitory activity against *E. coli* ATCC 25922, with an MIC value greater than 6.4 mg/L [25].

In Turkey, studies show that, essential oil from *Mentha piperita* (peppermint) was tested against both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*, *B. Cereus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*, *Salmonella spp.*) bacteria. Results indicated that the oil was more effective against Gram-positive bacteria, particularly *B. cereus*, which showed the largest inhibition zones. Concentrations of 25 and 50 µL/mL inhibited *B. cereus* and *S. aureus*, respectively, while 100 µL/mL was required to inhibit *E. coli* and *Salmonella spp.* The differences in susceptibility were attributed to structural and chemical variations in bacterial cell walls [26].

A study conducted in Azerbaijan assessed the antimicrobial effects of *S. officinalis* extracts against several pathogenic microorganisms, including *S. aureus* (strain 700699), *E. coli* (25922), *P. aeruginosa* (1022), *C. albicans* (2024), *B. anthracoides*, and *K. pneumoniae* (505562). The results demonstrated that sage extracts possess potential therapeutic importance in the treatment of oral cavity infections [27].

Another study examined mixtures of various Lamiaceae essential oils and purified white naphthalan oil, as well as their combinations with malic acid. Test microorganisms included methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), *B. anthracoides*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *C. albicans*. Results showed that mountain mint essential oil exhibited inhibition zones ranging from 5 to 20 mm (*E. coli* – 5 mm, *C. albicans* and *B. anthracoides* – 20 mm). However, its mixtures with naphthalan oil had no effect on *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae*, and only weak activity against some other microorganisms. Similarly, field mint essential oil alone exhibited inhibition zones of 5–20 mm (*K. pneumoniae* – 5 mm, *S. aureus* – 20 mm), but its mixtures showed minimal or no antimicrobial activity. These results suggest that while the individual oils display moderate to strong antimicrobial activity, their combinations may reduce or neutralize these effects [28].

These findings indicate that extracts and essential oils of mint, basil, thyme, rosemary, and sage belonging to the Lamiaceae family demonstrate significant antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Particularly, the essential oils of *T. vulgaris*, *O. basilicum*, and *R. officinalis* show high inhibitory effects against antibiotic-resistant strains. These results suggest that Lamiaceae plants could serve as potential natural alternatives or complementary agents in managing antibiotic-

resistant Gram-negative bacteria responsible for healthcare-associated infections. Future studies should further investigate their pharmacological profiles, toxicological properties, and clinical applications.

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